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Research Article

Afghan Public University Teachers' Perceptions of Teaching through Technology in the Classroom

Abdul Saboor Zaheeb^{1*} Abdul Samad Roshan², Ahmad Yaad³

¹Faculty of Education, Department of English Language and Literature, Kunduz University, Afghanistan

²Faculty of Languages and Literature. English Department, Shiekh Zayed University, Khost, Afghanistan

³ Faculty of Languages and Literature, English Department, Paktia University, Paktia Afghanistan

* **Abdul Saboor Zaheeb**

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Abstract: *This study aims to investigate Afghan public university teachers' perceptions of technology use in the classroom. Furthermore, the purpose of this research is to explore teachers' perceptions of technology use in the classroom for learning and teaching, technical support from, and online classes. The quantitative data, out of 55 respondents from different universities of Afghanistan, were collected and descriptively analyzed through using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) Version 26. The results of this study revealed that Afghan public university teachers' perceptions of using technology in the classroom were moderately positive. Notably, their perceptions were highly positive in learning and teaching through technology in the class. It is indicated that teaching through technology could affect both teachers' and students' academic performance and enhances the collaborative skills of them. Additionally, their perceptions toward online classes and technical support were moderately positive, and they believe that they are very interested in teaching online courses, but the technical support from the faculty and university has delayed the proper usage of technology in the classroom. Besides, it is revealed that university and faculty do not provide them the technical support for enhancing technology use in the classroom, for example, the instructional workshops, seminars, and hardware and software. Based on the findings, it is suggested to the Ministry of Higher Education (MOHE) in Afghanistan to encourage the culture of electronic teaching and learning online and provided them enough technical support and workshops on technology use in the classroom.*

Keywords: *Perceptions, Technology, Technical support, Online class*

1.Introduction

Technology use has bloomed the earthed data to every corner of the world. The growing potential and availability of technology make the relationship between people and technology as an essential part of daily life. In some instances, technology fundamentally changes the function of an individual's role, making the success of the system increasingly dependent on the credibility of this relationship (Loague *et al.*, 2018). Information technology has impacted our daily life and cannot develop and improve without it. According to Underwood (2009), technology has influenced our society to the point that our lives are now more and more dependent on this tool, and it has become an integral part of every daily life in the current era of the world. The impact of technology is now overgrowing, particularly on teaching and learning. In the past two decades, the evolution and rapid development of technology have made traditional teaching methods increasingly dated, and the incorporation of technology has become a significant facet of effective teaching (Negi *et al.*, 2011).

Undoubtfully, technology has vitalized the educational system in the world. Higgins *et al.* (2012) mentioned that evidence from the previous study shows that technology is effective in improving education and learning. Besides, a plethora of studies has investigated the different correlational reasons for the low rate of technology variation in the educational context. The most common reasons are the lack of technological education, perceptions toward technology, lack of technology training and support, lack of infrastructure, and lack of opportunities to observe technology-based classes (Vannatta and Beyerbach, 2000; Fullan, 2013; Camilleri and Camilleri, 2017; Jones, 2017). So far, only one research was conducted on Afghan EFL lecturers' perceptions about instruction technology use in the classroom (Noori, 2019), and there hasn't been conducted on all teachers in the public universities of Afghanistan and at the same time at different provinces of Afghanistan. Therefore, this study is aimed to investigate Afghan public university teachers' perceptions of technology use in the classroom. Particularly, to find out their perceptions about learning and teaching through technology, technical support from the universities and faculties, and online classes.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Teachers' Perceptions of technology in teaching and learning

The role of technology in education is fourfold: it is used as part of the curriculum, as an instructional delivery method, as a tool to support instructions and as a tool to improve the learning process as a whole. Education has gone from passive and reactive to interactive and ferocious, appreciations to technology (Raja and Nagasubramani, 2018). Technology is an authoritative learning provider when used to expand student engagement in a meaningful, intellectually authentic curriculum. Technology is just an instrument, and it is beneficial for the students to select it. It should be chosen when students need to know it effectively. Technology is a powerful contributor to learning if it is used to deepen students' engagement in a meaningful and

intellectually authentic curriculum. Technology is a tool. It should be selected when it is the best tool for students to learn (DePasquale *et al.*, 2003; Murphy *et al.*, 2003). Nowadays, information technology is a worthwhile tool for enhancing the ability to educate and learn. With the aid of IT, audio-visual education can be given with ease. In all contexts of teaching-learning, a computer is a useful tool. In schools, colleges, multi-media technologies are used to communicate ideas between students and teachers (Bhakta and Dutta, 2016).

Education technology can make learner-centered and collaborative — and this can help students engage more effectively with information from the course. They learn by doing, instead of memorizing the facts. The classroom does not have walls anymore. There are no limits left to the learning environment. And guidance may be provided by any number of subject matter experts — besides the person who is teaching the course (Gan *et al.*, 2015). Students can use online tools anytime they need it, and teachers will see which students may need additional support. Practicing self-paced learning also helps students learn digital literacy and skills of the 21st century, which will be useful when entering the workforce. Students can access resources online whenever they need to, and instructors can see which students might need extra help. The exercise of self-paced learning also helps students learn digital literacy and 21st-century skills, which will be useful when they enter the workforce. Technology changes the way we access information, but also how we're taught that information. The instructor becomes less of a 'sage on the stage' and more of a 'guide on the side.' From accessing course materials online to watching video-recorded lectures, technology opens up the possibility for teaching innovation: from collaborative group work to flipped and hybrid classrooms (Miller and Skinner, 2015; Atifnigar, Alokozay, Wahidullah, Zaheer, *et al.*, 2020).

2.2 Teachers' Perceptions of Technical Support

Many higher education instructors are making a concentrated effort to infuse their teaching with technology in order to become more successful teachers (Moseley, 2010). Nicolle and Lou (2008) indicated that numerous faculty members imagine there is an advantage in their teaching from using some level of technology, even in cases where they have not yet integrated technology into their classes (Nicolle and Lou, 2008). It has been found that professional development, technical and administrative support, and teacher beliefs played an influential role in whether teachers felt prepared to use laptops in the classroom and, in turn, whether they actually did so (Inan and Lowther, 2010). However, a study by Tong and Trinidad (2005), they revealed if teachers are not provided with technical support, they would be frustrated to use ICT. Lack of technical support frustrates teachers in their classrooms by integrating computer technology. The investigator investigated whether the above factors could increase the use of computer technology by teachers.

When the technology became a more accessible system for teachers to access and use technology that was already developed, the mentor started discussing the lack of technological skills, developing a common vision for technology use inside universities. Workshops and training

are provided for increasing teachers' knowledge about technical skills such as method sharing and using laptops and necessary software skills. These activities were situated in teachers' needs by assessing progress on school-wide technology goals. These activities were situated in teachers' needs by regularly assessing progress on school-wide technology goals and aligning technology-integration efforts with existing school initiatives. These activities lasted approximately two months (Kopcha, 2012).

In addition, perceptions of teachers is a strongly bounded with the use of information communication technology (ICT), which gives escalation to positive pedagogical approaches focused on various styles of learning (acquisition of knowledge, deepening of knowledge, and development of education) in colleges of education (Unesco, 2011). Furthermore, Shin and Son (2007) revealed that most teachers in the study believe that the internet can be an effective tool for finding authentic resources, sharing information, communicating with target language speakers, and motivating students. However, the only drawbacks teachers have in using technology will be the lack of hardware, inadequate time to plan lessons based on technology, and lack of technical support (Nikian *et al.*, 2013; Atifnigar *et al.*, 2020).

2.3. Teachers' Perceptions of Online Courses

Technology-based learning allows universities to expand their current geographical reach, focus on new prospective students, and develop themselves as global providers of education. The waves of technology are progressing rapidly, and teachers in higher education are looking for web-enhanced classes online to stay drifting among the stream of technology. The internet changed how classes are held. 'It's been found to be convenient and can allow students to access educational material quickly, which can support better communication between students and lecturers (Mapuva, 2009). One area in which technology has influenced the educational environment is the brisk improvement of online learning (Allen and Seaman, 2013; Nijat *et al.*, 2019). Moreover, (Allen and Seaman, 2013) reported that one of the main concerns of faculty is to deal with the quality of online services. They asserted that a more significant number of academic members in the faculty find online learning very less than compared to face to face learning. However, those academic teachers at universities where online classes are presented are more likely to take a favorable view of online learning (Safi and Kumar, 2019)

3. Materials and methods

This study was based on a quantitative research design. An online survey questionnaire was used to collect quantitative data from the respondents from different universities in Afghanistan. The data from the findings were descriptively analyzed through using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 24 in terms of mean and percentage in which the highest positive perceptions mean was calculated that was above 4, moderate positive perceptions above 3 and negative perceptions was below 3, respectively. The questionnaire used in this study was adopted from Loague *et al.* (2018) in which the reliability test was conducted, and Cronbach's

Alpha value was above .70, which is a highly consistent scale. The questionnaire was distributed through online service in google form to 70 Afghan public university teachers, and 55 of the respondents in the questionnaire. The questionnaire was consisting of four sections. (i) demographic of the respondents, (ii) learning and teaching (5 items), (iii) technical support (6 items), online classes (7 items).

4. Findings

4.1 Demographic characteristics of the participants

The survey questionnaire was distributed to the teachers at the different universities of Afghanistan. The data was collected from Kabul, Kandahar, Nangarhar, Herat, Alberoni, Khost, Laghman, Helmand, Panjshir, and Jawzjan universities of Afghanistan. The data obtained from the online survey questionnaire about the demography of the participants revealed that most of the participants are male (83.6%), and the rest of them were female (16.4%). Most of the respondents are aging between 30-39 (67.3%) years old, followed by 20-29 (25.5%), and a few of them are (7.3%), respectively. Regarding the teaching experience of the participants, the data revealed that most of them are possessing 6-10 (58.2%) years of teaching in their relevant fields, followed by 1-5 (29.1%), and 11-15 (12.7%). Furthermore, it has been found that most of the Afghan University lecturers have available technological tools in the classroom, which are only laptops and projectors, and most of them preferred to use technology in the classroom.

4.2 The overall perceptions of teachers toward the use of technology in the classroom

This section describes the overall perceptions of teachers toward the use of technology in the classroom, particularly for learning and teaching, technical support from the faculty, and holding the online course to enhance both teaching and learning.

Table 1 Technology Use in the Classroom

No		Mean	Percentage
1	Learning Instruction	4.05	81%
2	Technical Support	3.11	62.2%
3	Online Courses	3.29	65.8%
	Overall	3.48	69.66%

The data from table 1.1 shows that teachers' perceptions toward the use of technology in the classroom is in a moderate positive. To be more specific, teachers' perceptions about learning and instruction is high positive, while for technical support and online courses are moderate positive.

4.3 Teachers' Perceptions of Learning Teaching

The following table shows the data obtained from the questionnaire about the teachers' perceptions of technology in the classroom for learning and teaching.

Table 2 Learning and Teaching

No	Statements	Mean	Percentage
1	Teacher use of technology in a class has an impact on learning.	4.30	86%
2	Student use of technology in a class has an impact on learning.	4.01	80.2%
3	Technology increases student collaboration in a classroom	4.23	84.6%
4	I encourage the use of smartphones in my class for instructional/learning purposes.	3.74	74.8%
5	I encourage the use of laptops in my class for instructional/learning purposes.	3.98	79.6%

As can be observed from the table above, most of the teachers believe that the use of technology in the classroom affects both teachers' and students' learning (86%;80.2%), and also increase student cooperation in the classroom (84.6%). At the same time, most of the teachers believed that they encourage the utility of smartphones and laptops in their classes for the purpose of teaching and learning (74.8%; 79.6%).

4.4 Teachers' Perceptions of technology use in the classroom for technical support

This section describes the findings regarding the technical support from the faculty, university, and related information communication technology (ICT) services office.

3 Technical Support

No	Statements	Mean	Percentage
1	The university provides instructional technology workshops.	3.23	64.6%
2	The university provides hardware and software.	3.09	61.8%
3	My faculty provides instructional technology workshops	2.92	58.4%
4	My faculty provides hardware and software.	3.10	62%
5	I seek technology to help from other faculty members.	3.10	62%

6	I seek technology help from the Office of Technology Services.	3.23	64.6%
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The table above indicates the result of the teachers' perceptions technology use in the classroom for the technical support from their relevant organization, most of the teachers' perceptions about the provision of instructional technology workshop, hardware, and software from the university and faculty was at a moderate level (64.6%; 61.8%;58.4%; 62%). Also, they asserted that they ask for help from other faculty members, and the Office of Technology Services when facing problems in using technology in the classroom (62%; 64.5%).

4.5 Teachers' Perceptions of technology use in the classroom for Online Courses

The following tables describe the findings from the teachers' point of view about the technology used in the classroom for the provision, conduction, and outcome of online classes when teaching and learning.

Table 4 Online Classes

No	Statements	Mean	Percentage
1	Learning outcomes are the same in an online course as a face-to-face course.	2.78	55.6%
2	The quality of an online course is the same as a face-to-face course.	2.61	52.2%
3	Faculty-student interaction is essential in an online course.	3.96	79.2%
4	I have taken online courses.	3.49	69.8%
5	I have taught online courses.	3.10	62%
6	I would like to teach an online course.	4.20	84%
7	Instructional models used in online courses are the same as those used in face-to-face classes.	2.89	57.8%

As can be indicated from the table above that average numbers of the teachers' perceptions are slightly moderate toward the outcome, and quality of online classes compare to the face to face classes (55.6%; 52.2%). Amazingly, most of them believe that interaction between the faculty members and the students is essential in online courses (79.2%) and are in favor of teaching online classes (84%). Besides, teachers' perceptions regarding the online courses are slightly moderate, meaning they have taken online (69.8%), taught online classes (62%), and even teaching models used in online courses are the same as those used in face-to-face classes (57.8).

6. Discussion

In the most education context, teacher perceptions are one of the leading factors that adopt educational technology tools in teaching and learning. Perceptions of teachers are strongly bonded with the use of information communication technology (ICT), which gives escalation to positive pedagogical approaches focused on various styles of learning (acquisition of knowledge, deepening of knowledge, and development of education) in colleges of education (Unesco, 2011). After analyzing the online survey questionnaire from different university teachers in Afghanistan, we concluded that teachers' perceptions toward using technology in the classroom was moderately positive, mainly their perceptions were high positive to learning and teaching compared to the technical support and teaching online classes. This might be due to non-practically and encourages teachers from the ministry toward technology use in the classroom. In line with our findings, a study conducted by Noori (2019) on Afghan EFL teachers toward instructional technology in Afghanistan revealed that there was a high positive perception but a moderate utility of instructional technology by the teachers in their classroom.

In contrast, a study conducted by Safitry et al. (2015), they revealed that the teachers have a positive perspective towards applying ICT in their classrooms, even though they lack technical support from the schools and lack of ICT proficiency. The research revealed at the initial surveys, and teachers show a highly positive trend in the perceptions of instructional technology's value (Lea et al., 2001). Besides, The analysis of Mundy *et al.* (2012) has indicated that faculty members need not only to learn how to use technology at a basic level but also to learn how to integrate that technology into their curricula. Also, newer teachers from digital native generations must be taught how their acquired skills can be used to integrate technology into the classroom curriculum to provide complex cognitive engagement for their students.

The findings of this research revealed that teachers' perceptions of the use of technology for teaching and learning were high positive because technology use in the classroom can affect both teachers' and students' performance and increases collaboration among them. Such perceptions toward technology use for teaching-learning might be due to the high accessibility of computers, mobiles, teaching materials, and meeting the current needs of the technological era. Also, teaching with a plethora of video, audio, text from the internet made teaching and learning more exciting in the Afghani context. In line with this, Bequette (2019) mentioned that teachers could also use computers to describe various tasks in real-time, such as providing students with simulations of how substances perform in science classrooms at various temperatures or showing videos and video footage of significant historical events which allow the Teacher to provoke deeper processes of thinking. Several young generations who have used computers both in and out of the classroom over the past two decades will acknowledge the use of an informal and essential approach to computer use in education, as well as accept it.

In addition, it has been revealed that teachers' perceptions of online classes were also slightly moderate but not positive. It has resulted that most of the teachers are interested in teaching

online classes which can be considered as a new and modern factor of teaching since teaching through technology is new in Afghanistan, and therefore, most the Teacher prefers online classes. Similarly, a study conducted by (Galea (2019), participants agreed that face-to-face learning is better appropriate in the discipline, but some noted that if online classes are used with proper training, then it can be effective and efficient. Moreover, Steinert *et al.* (2019) also indicated that faculty who were teaching online was grateful when institutions provided mentoring, training, support, and recognition of their success. Moreover, most of the teachers also argued that online classes could boost up teachers' and student interaction, and they said that outcome of the online and face to face classes are the same. This finding has resembled with findings of Pamela (2006), she indicated that all teachers are equally persuaded that ICT is an important and useful tool to enable them to communicate or present their teaching as students are more involved in interactive classes than in modern or digital methods.

In contrast, the findings resulted that teachers' perceptions toward technology use in the classroom for technical support and online classes is slightly moderate, which is not considered as a positive perception. Most of the teachers believe that university and faculty showed declination in providing any instructional workshops, hardware, and software for ameliorating and adopting technological tools in the classroom. Sometimes they seek help from other faculty members and university-related ICT service office to solve their problems. Likewise, our findings have resembled with results of Loague *et al.* (2018); they found that the university is parallel with other schools, and the faculty is conducting technology use with intermated levels. In addition, Lodhi *et al.* (2019) asserted that some factors stopped teachers from integrating computer technology. They are the significance of hardware/software and technical support, the lack of effective training, lack of planning for computer technology integration, and lack of material support. Moreover, the only drawbacks most of the teachers have in using technology are the lack of hardware, inadequate time to plan lessons based on technology, and lack of technical support (Nikian *et al.*, 2013).

6. Conclusion

This study was aimed to examine Afghan public university teachers' perceptions about technology use in the classroom. It has resulted that most of the teachers preferred technology use in the classroom, and their perceptions were moderately positive toward it. More specifically, teachers' perceptions toward learning and teaching via technology was highly positive. They believed that teaching through technology could affect both teachers' and students' academic performance and enhances the collaborative skills of them. On the other hand, in this study, teachers' perceptions toward technology use in the classroom for technical support was slightly moderate positive. They believed that university and faculty do not provide technical support for enhancing technology use in the classroom, for example, the instructional workshops, seminars, and hardware and software. Moreover, teachers' perceptions of online classes were also slightly moderate positive. They asserted that they are very interested in teaching online, but the technical support from the faculty and university has delayed the proper usage of technology in the classroom. Finally, it is suggested that university authority should strive to encourage the culture

of electronic teaching and to learn among teachers and students at the university level in Afghanistan and provide technical support, workshops, seminars to boost the use of technology in the classroom.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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